

ERRATUM

Figure 2, page 70, of the following article

ÁVILA, S. P., SANTOS, A. C., PENTEADO, A. M., RODRIGUES, A. M., QUINTINO, I. AND MACHADO, M. I. The molluscs of the intertidal algal turf in the Azores. *Iberus*, 23 (1): 67-76.

was printed with a mistake. The correct figure (with the names *Littorina striata* and *Melarhappe neritoides* correctly placed) is included here.

Figure 2. Transect performed at Poça do Pano (Lajes do Pico, Pico island) and vertical distribution of rocky shore organisms. HWST: mean high water level at spring tides; LWST: mean low water level at spring tides.

Figura 2. Transecto realizado en Poça do Pano (Lajes do Pico, isla de Pico) y distribución vertical de organismos de costa rocosa. HWST: nivel medio superior del agua en mareas de primavera. LWST: nivel medio inferior del agua en mareas de primavera.